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Table of Content - Volume 05 Issue 10 (October) 2025

NO.	ARTICLE TITLE	AUTHOR NAME	PAGE NO.
1.	The Historical Development And Cultural Significance Of Khorezm Khalfachilik Art	Khabibullayeva Mavluda Adambayevna	5-8
2.	Addressing the Decline in Teaching Professionalism: Empowering Educators to Improve Pedagogy Through Action Research	Ethan Davis, Ava Johnson	9-12
3.	Five initiatives and its role in raising the spirituality of youths	Haty Neman	13-15
4.	Musical means of forming a positive emotional state through percussion instruments	Samatov Temur Alisher ugli	16-19
5.	Using innovative technologies in teaching English to medical students	Michaela Mushuchik	20-22
6.	The importance of developing the spiritual and moral competence of young people	Raxmonova Gullola Shavkatovna	23-24
7.	The content of the integrative approach and its role in the formation of creative thinking in students	Ergasheva Fayoz Bahodir qizi	25-27
8.	Teaching didactic lessons based on problematic situations in drawing classes	Gulomova Nozima Khotamovna	28-31
9	The role of involving students in design activities in the concept of modern technology education	Jabborova Umida Yusupovna	32-34
10	Teaching effectively and productively academic writing skill in higher school pupils	Ibadova Farida Maxmarajabovna	35-37
11.	Issues of developing students' communicative competence in modern educational settings	Akmaljon Yusufovich Akhmedov	38-42
12.	Some Issues of Teaching The Uzbek Language As A Sister Language in Higher Education	Sh.Sh.Yuldasheva	43-46
13.	The Importance of Teaching Methods for Rubob	Saitov Jaqsiliq Jarilqasinovich	47-48
14.	Model for the Development of Students' Creative Competence in The Process of Teaching English	Seilkhanova R.N.	49-51
15.	Recreational Tourism and Healthy Lifestyle: Pedagogical Opportunities	Nuriyman Sultanzade	52-59
16.	The Role of National Values in Shaping the Aesthetic Worldview of Schoolchildren	Kurbanova Rita Jarasovna, Saidbaeva Barno Endirboy kizi	60-67

THE HISTORICAL DEVELOPMENT AND CULTURAL SIGNIFICANCE OF KHOREZM KHALFACHILIK ART

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Abstract. This article explores the historical formation and cultural significance of the Khalfachilik art of Khorezm. Special attention is given to the role of women in preserving this creative tradition, its function in wedding and ritual ceremonies, and the contemporary efforts to protect and transmit this unique cultural heritage to future generations.

Keywords: Khalfachilik, Khorezm, folk art, ritual songs, women’s creativity, cultural heritage, national traditions, music, dance.

Introduction. The Khorezm oasis occupies a special place in the rich cultural heritage of the Uzbek people. For centuries, this region has been distinguished by its unique folk oral art, musical and dance traditions, and wedding and ceremonial culture. The art of Khorezm khalfachilik was formed on the basis of these rich traditions, and it is not only a bright example of women's creativity, but also a cultural phenomenon that occupies an important place in the social life of the people.

Khalfachilik is a synthesis of song, dance and word art performed mainly by women, reflecting all aspects of folk life. Khalfachilik are creators who delight the people, unite them, and express national identity during ceremonies such as weddings, cradle weddings, circumcision weddings, and holidays.

Contents. The art of Khorezmian khalfa has its long historical roots, and it was formed by feeding on the religious, cultural and aesthetic traditions of Central Asia. Historical sources indicate that the first elements of khalfa appeared during the Zoroastrian era, when individuals called “kalpa” or “karpa” acted as prayer leaders performing religious rituals.

Reading the texts of the “Avesta” in melody and propagating them was one of the first functional manifestations of khalfa.

After the introduction of Islam, the art of khalfa changed its form and turned from a means of religious and moral propaganda into an artistic performing art. Especially in the second half of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century, during the Khiva Khanate, the art of khalfa became an important component of cultural life. During the reign of Muhammad Rahimkhan Soni, the activities of writers and artists gathered

around the palace had a great influence on the rise of Khorezm culture. The formation of khalfa among women is a unique social and spiritual phenomenon. Khalfas were usually literate, intelligent, with the ability to speak and sing. They were respected among the people in the sense of "knowledgeable", "teacher", "leader". Thus, the word "khalfa" gradually emerged from its religious meaning and began to acquire a cultural and educational meaning. Khalfas participated in women's circles, weddings and ceremonies as the main performers, singing folk epics, lapar, yalla and terma. Researcher T. Jalolov noted that "khalfas were the queens of women's parties", who gave spirit, joy and pleasure to the ceremonies through their melodies and songs. This situation demonstrates the aesthetic and psychological importance of the art of weaving in the everyday life of the people.

Khorezmian khalfism is divided into three groups according to the types of performance: creative-poetic khalfas, bookish (solo) khalfas and performing (song) khalfas.

Creative-poetic khalfas sang epics, wrote poems, and created musical works; bookish khalfas recited epics and religious books from memory and performed them at ceremonies; performing khalfas served as live performers at weddings, holidays, and ceremonies. In their performance, genres such as "yor-yor", "kelin salom", "lapar", and "terma" sounded with their own artistic analysis and melody.

The introduction of the harmonium instrument into Khorezm art at the end of the 19th and beginning of the 20th centuries led to the professional rise of khalfa performance. As a result of research, it was found that the harmonium was brought to Khorezm from Tortkul by Kurban Ota Ismailov, through whom it became popular in the Khiva palace. Later, the harmonium also spread widely among female khalfas, renewing their creative style and creating new timbre and melody possibilities.

By the end of the 20th century, this art began to be recognized at a high level. The establishment of a "khalfa" class at the Khiva City Music School in 1989 on the initiative of Ozod Zaripov was an important stage in the systematic study of this direction and its introduction to the younger generation. The services of the People's Artist of Uzbekistan Gavharkhanim Rakhimova in this process are of particular importance. The awarding of the first-class diploma to the students of this class at the Children's Folklore Festival held in the Republic of Ukraine in 1992 is an international recognition of the art of khalfa.

Today, the art of khalfa is taught in music and art schools, folklore ensembles in the Khorezm region, retaining its significance as a national and

cultural value. This art demonstrates the social activity of women, the continuity of folk oral creativity, and the continuity of cultural heritage.

Research work. The direction of khalfa art, which was formed in the Khorezm oasis, began to be scientifically studied by a number of Uzbek and foreign researchers from the second half of the 20th century. Initial research on the art of khalfa was studied in the system of folk songs, lapar and yalla of Khorezm folklore, and today it is recognized as an important form of women's creativity, oral tradition, and social communication.

S.N. Ergashevna in her research analyzes the source bases of the Khorezm khalfa heritage and notes the presence of traces of this art in manuscripts and archival documents. She substantiates with scientific evidence the direct and inextricable connection of the main epics and ceremonial songs in the Khalfa repertoire with the traditional performance of the beshi. This fact shows that Khalfa is not only a women's creativity, but also an integral part of the broader folklore system. [1;p. 44]

U. Kurbanova in her article “The Role of Khorezm Khalfa Art in Uzbek Folk Performance” highlights the socio-spiritual significance of Khalfa art. According to the author, Khalfa has long served as a cultural bridge that ensured the unity of Khorezm women in weddings and ceremonies. Through the lapars, yalla and ceremonial songs performed by Khalfas, social values, family etiquette and religious beliefs were passed down from generation to generation. This approach allows us to view Khalfa art not only as a musical phenomenon, but also as a socio-cultural phenomenon. [2;p. 127]

D. Hamidova studies the development of the art of khalfa in modern times. According to her, today khalfa schools, folk festivals and women's ensembles operate in the Khorezm region. Also, some examples of this direction are included in the list of intangible cultural heritage of Uzbekistan. Hamidova's research substantiates the need to preserve the art of khalfa, promote it among the younger generation and integrate it into the education system. [3; p. 48]

R.O. Ismatullaeva and A.Kh. Trigulova in their article “Khalfa Art in Khorezm” published on the Zenodo platform analyzed the role of khalfa in women's vocal culture. Researchers interpret this art as a kind of women's folklore school, considering it a means of preserving cultural identity and oral history [4; p. 12]. This article shows the growing scientific attention to the art of khalfa among foreign audiences.

According to the results of the analysis, the art of khalfa is being re-evaluated today not only as a rich heritage of folk oral creativity, but also as a

phenomenon reflecting cultural identity and social solidarity. The research of Uzbek and foreign researchers deeply illuminates the stages of historical formation of this art, its socio-spiritual functions and modern significance. Therefore, a comprehensive study of the art of khalfa from a scientific, educational and cultural point of view is one of the urgent tasks for the future development of the cultural heritage of Uzbekistan.

Conclusion. The art of Khorezm khalfa with its deep historical roots, social and aesthetic essence is an integral part of our national culture. It is a unique oral and musical heritage that expresses the philosophy of life, worldview, and hopes of the people.

Preservation, scientific study and transfer of this art to a new generation are urgent issues today. Halfa craftsmanship is not only the art of the past generation, but also an invaluable asset that strengthens our national identity and cultural unity.

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